

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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The role of radiation oncology in the treatment of malignant tumors in children

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Radiotherapy is an effective modality of treatment and an integral part of treatment for many pediatric malignancies. Advances in radiotherapy such as highly conformal techniques have led to a new era of precise treatment with significant reduction of healthy tissue exposed to radiation. On the other hand imaging guided radiotherapy has improved daily precise positioning of the patient. Inaccuracy in daily positioning is now reduced to a minimum. The wide margins that encompassed healthy tissue are now much smaller. Highly conformal techniques, with imaging guided radiotherapy have led to significant advances in precise dose delivery to the target volume. Given that a large number of children achieve long term survival, the late effects of radiotherapy are a topic of great interest. In pediatric radiation oncology protection of surrounding tissue and organs in growth and development are of great importance. Three dimensional conformal radiotherapy (3DCRT) is the basis for advanced conformal techniques: intensity modulated radiotherapy (IMRT), volumetric arc therapy (VMAT) and stereotaxic radiotherapy. Additionally with proton radiotherapy, which is applied in the treatment of younger children and specific sites, pediatric radiation oncology has the ability to respond to the modern needs of pediatric oncology. According to recommendations and current pediatric radiation oncology protocols of treatment IMRT technique is widely used, 3DCRT is still the standard for craniospinal radiotherapy and some other localisation, while the VMAT technique is used in selected cases. There is great interest in the use of stereotaxic radiotherapy, while proton beam recommendations in pediatric radiation oncology continue.

Keywords: radiotherapy, pediatric malignancies, technique

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